

Role of Defects in Recovery of Radiolytic Damage in Irradiated Potassium Nitrate

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The role of lattice defects introduced by doping and crushing in the thermal annealing of γ -irradiated potassium nitrate as well as the effect of crushing in the recovery process of doped (Ba^{2+}) crystals has been studied. It is seen that the doped crystals are more susceptible to recovery than the pure substance above the temperature of 400 K crystal transition (rhombic $\rightleftharpoons$ trigonal). The data show that in both the substances crushing prior to irradiation enhances the rate of recovery, whereas subsequent to irradiation lowers the rate.

A crystalline substance ordinarily contains a fair concentration of defects such as interstitials and vacancies. Further defects are introduced by crushing, compression, doping, fast neutron bombardment¹⁻⁷, etc. The influence of defects on the initial damage and in the subsequent recovery of damage species has been studied by many workers⁸⁻¹⁰. It is interesting to have a comparative study of annealing in pure and doped (Ba^{2+}) potassium nitrate, also the effect of crushing prior and subsequent to irradiation on the recovery process of those crystals.

Experimental

Doped crystals (1.0 mol %) of potassium and barium nitrate (A.R., B.D.H) were prepared following the standard procedure¹¹. The mixed crystals were cooled in a desiccator, crushed in an agate mortar and dried at 383 K for 10 h. Irradiation was carried out in glass ampoules at room temperature with cobalt-60 γ -rays to a dose of 6.0×10^{-1} MGY at the dose rate of 0.102×10^{-2} MGY h⁻¹. A portion of the pure as well as doped crystals was crushed into fine powder prior and subsequent to irradiation. The damage nitrite was estimated spectrophotometrically by diazocolour reaction^{12,13}. Isothermal recovery studies in pure and doped crystals were carried out between 403 to 433 K and in crushed substances at 423 K by following the procedure described elsewhere¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The colours of the crystals were not much affected by irradiation and the damage induced in pure and doped (Ba^{2+}) potassium nitrate by cobalt-60 gamma-rays are respectively 66.49 and 63.27 μ mol NO_2^- g⁻¹. The lower initial damage in the doped crystals than in the pure salt may be ascribed¹⁴ to competition between dopant (Ba^{2+})

and the radiolytic damage fragments for the electrons involved in the radiation chemical processes. The data show (Fig. 1) that both the crystals undergo an abrupt recovery above the temperature of 400 K

crystal transition (rhombic $\rightleftharpoons$ trigonal). The susceptibility of doped crystals to thermal recovery than the pure salt is due to the generation of cationic vacancies^{15,16} in the crystal lattice of potassium nitrate by the divalent Ba^{2+} which increases the free space and consequently accelerates the migration of the mobile fragments. Direct recovery induced in the pure crystals by crushing is negligible, whereas very low value ($\varphi=0.022$) is obtained in doped crystals.

Fig. 1. Annealing of nitrite in gamma-irradiated pure and doped (Ba^{2+}) potassium nitrate.

TABLE I—EFFECT OF CRUSHING IN THE THERMAL ANNEALING OF PURE AND DOPED (Ba^{2+}) POTASSIUM NITRATE

Substance	Untreated	Crushed prior to irradiation	Crushed subsequent to irradiation
	Fraction annealed, φ		
KNO_3	0.092	0.159	0.048
$KNO_3(Ba^{2+})$	0.791	0.822	0.651

Fig. 2. Influence of crushing on isothermal annealing in gamma-irradiated pure and doped (Ba²⁺) potassium nitrate.

It is seen that in both pure as well as doped crystals, crushing prior to irradiation enhances the rate of recovery, whereas subsequent to irradiation retards the process. During crushing an activated creep or plastic flow process^{6,17-19} occurs in the crystal lattice generating vacancies and interstitials, which causes local strain²⁰ in the lattice resulting decrease in the activation energy for the migration of the mobile fragments (NO₂⁻ or O₂/O) towards the other stationary species (O₂/O or NO₂⁻). The consequent increase in the jump-frequency results in direct recovery and in the higher rate of thermal annealing is observed. The local strain produced also lowers the potential^{18,19} barrier for the release of the trapped fragments more possibly O₂, thereby contributing to the direct recovery. The above phenomenon

occurs in the crystals subjected to crushing prior to irradiation. The rate and magnitude of annealing in both the crystals is lower than the untreated salts when crushing is carried out after irradiation. During crushing the trapped oxygen (O₂) is released and escape out of the crystal lattice causing low recovery.

References

1. S. R. MOHANTY and S. R. UPADHYAY, *Nature (London)*, 1963, 199, 169; 1964, 201, 921.
2. T. ANDERSEN, *Nature (London)*, 1963, 200, 1094.
3. M. KHARR and S. R. MOHANTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 1527.
4. M. KHARR and S. R. MOHANTY, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1967, 8, 63.
5. S. R. MOHANTY and E. M. K. NAIR, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1970, 13, 87.
6. T. ANDERSEN and A. G. MADDOCK, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 2362.
7. T. ANDERSEN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, 59, 2625.
8. S. R. MOHANTY and V. M. PANDEY, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1975, 34, 196.
9. D. BHATTA, S. R. MOHANTY and K. O. SAMANTRAY, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1981, 28, 13.
10. B. M. MAHAPATRA and D. BHATTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 512.
11. V. V. BOLDYREV, V. M. LYKHIN, A. N. OBLIVANTSEV and K. M. SALIKHOV, *Kinet. Catal.*, 1966, 7, 383.
12. M. B. SHINN *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 13, 33.
13. N. F. KERSHAW and N. S. CHAMBERLIN, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1942, 14, 312.
14. V. V. GROMOV, *Russ Chem. Rev. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1974, 43, 201.
15. J. CUNNINGHAM in "Radical Ions", eds. K. T. KAISER and L. KEVAN, Interscience, New York, 1968, p. 475.
16. YU. A. ZAKHAROV and E. P. ABAKUMOV, *ISZ. Tomsk. Politekh. Inst.*, 1970, 176, 10.
17. F. SEITZ, *Phys. Rev.*, 1950, 80, 239.
18. F. G. FRANK and W. T. READ, *Phys. Rev.*, 1950, 79, 722.
19. F. SEITZ, *Adv. Phys.*, 1952, 1, 43.
20. A. W. OVERHAUSER, *Phys. Rev.*, 1953, 90, 393.